

ISic3510

Epitaph for Lucius Ostrius Crescens

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.07.20 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found within a funerary building within the area designated 'recinto B' by Paolo Orsi during excavation in 1914 of the

Coordinates

38.1992517, 15.5566385

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale
interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory A3560

Physical Description

A slightly irregular small tablet of marble

Dimensions

Height 16 cm
Width 20.5 cm
Depth 3 cm

Layout

Four lines of Latin letters approximately centred on the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Thinly but deeply incised regular letters with minimal serifs and of slightly uneven size. R has a small open eye, with a long straight tail; E is fully perpendicular with equal length strokes; M is made up four equal oblique strokes reaching to top and bottom of the line.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 25 mm
Line 2: 20-22 mm
Lines 3-4: 20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 4: 9-14 mm

Text

1. · D(is) · M(anibus) ·
2. L(ucius) · Ostrius Cres
3. cens
4. vix(it) ann(is) · LXXVI

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 Photograph

Translation (en)

To the shades of the underworld. Lucius Ostrius Crescens died at 76 years of age

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284772

EDR 033612

EDCS 14805793

PHI 313626

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 3
Orsi, P. 1916. Messana. La necropoli romana di S. Placido e di altre scoperte avvenute nel 1910-1915. *Monumenti Antichi*. 24: 121-218. At 134

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3510. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358648>